

TABLE 1—6-[2-AMINO (AND SUBSTITUTED AMINO)-4-THIAZOLYT] BENZOTHAZOLES(II)

Sr. No.	R	R'	Cryst. from	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analytical Data			
							Found		Required	
							S	N	S	N
1.	H	H	A	166-8	66	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₃ S ₂	27.10	17.78	27.48	18.02
2.	H	Phenyl	A	176	51	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	20.42	13.20	20.71	13.59
3.	H	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	A	217	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ S ₂	18.38	12.22	18.63	12.23
4.	H	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	A	168	57	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ S ₂	18.29	12.02	18.63	12.23
5.	H	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	A	195	54	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	19.51	12.75	19.81	13.00
6.	H	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	A	140	56	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	19.60	13.47	19.81	13.00
7.	H	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	A	172	61	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS ₂	19.00	12.28	18.88	12.39
8.	H	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	A	250 ^d	55	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	18.30	15.45	18.08	15.82
9.	CH ₃	H	C	226	65	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	25.69	17.06	25.91	17.00
10.	CH ₃	Phenyl	D	181	55	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	19.38	12.72	19.81	13.00
11.	CF ₃	H	C	162	53	C ₁₁ H ₆ F ₃ N ₃ S ₂	*	13.64	—	13.95
12.	CF ₃	Phenyl	C	171	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ F ₃ N ₃ S ₂	**	11.55	—	11.14
13.	CF ₃	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	B	155	53	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ F ₃ N ₃ OS ₂	—	9.98	—	10.32
14.	CF ₃	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	B	163	58	C ₁₇ H ₉ ClF ₃ N ₃ S ₂	—	9.92	—	10.21
15.	C ₆ H ₅	H	B	230	53	C ₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	20.36	13.34	20.71	13.59
16.	C ₆ H ₅	Phenyl	C	212-3	50	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂	17.01	10.99	16.62	10.91

* Found : C, 43.52 ; H, 1.68. Required C, 43.85 ; H, 1.99.

** Found : C, 53.94 ; H, 2.65. Required C, 54.11 ; H, 2.65.

A=Alcohol ; B=Alcohol/water ; C=Benzen ; D=Benzene/pet.ether (60°-80°) ;
E=Xylene · F=Acetic acid.

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Studies on the Infra-red Spectra of Synthetic Humic Acids.

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SEVERAL workers¹⁻⁵ have described the use of infra-red spectroscopy to obtain information about the various atomic groupings and functional groups in soil humic substances and synthesised humus like substances. Flaig⁶ has, however observed that i-r spectra of natural humic acids, synthetic humic acids formed by oxidation of polyphenols and lignin fractions isolated from rotted straw are relatively uncharacteristic, but Ziechmann⁷ shows that well defined absorption occurs at 7-9 μ and at about 10 μ for various peats and synthetic humic acid preparations. A comparative study of the spectra of humic acid from peat, lignite and oxidised hydroquinone with those of various chars and

coals has been made by Elofson⁸. The present communication deals with comparative studies of the i-r spectra of the synthetic humic substances prepared from different monomers with a view to compare their structural pattern.

Experimental

The methods of preparing the synthetic humic substances have been described in detail earlier⁹. The i. r. spectra in KBr disc (1 mg sample and 300 mg KBr) were recorded on Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer over the region 2.5 μ to 14 μ . The following electro-dialysed samples have been studied :

(i) Hydroquinone humic acid, (ii) Hydroquinone glycine polymer, (iii) catechol humic acid (by O₂), (iv) glucose humic acid, (v) glucose humatmelanic acid, (vi) glucose humic acid (40 hours) and (vii) the nonhydrolysable residues from acid hydrolysis of (a) hydroquinone humic acid, (b) catechol humic acid (c) catechol humic acid (by O₂) and (d) hydroquinone glycine polymer respectively.

Results and Discussion

The infra-red spectra of the different humic acid preparations bear a striking resemblance to one another suggesting that in spite of monomer differences, the polymer formed are closely related structurally. The spectra are, however too diffuse to reveal any significant structural detail. From the data obtained by us the following absorption bands are to be noted particularly in the region 3.45 μ , 5.8 to 5.9 μ , 6.25 to 6.3 μ , 6.6 to 6.7 μ , 7.15 to 7.4 μ , 8.0 to 8.3 μ and 9.8 μ . The relative intensities and sharpness of the contours of the bands are described in Table 1.

TABLE-1 ABSORPTION BANDS AND DESCRIPTION OF THEIR CONTOURS.

Hydroquinone H.A	2.9-3.0 μ broad	3.45 μ hump	5.85 μ hump	6.25 μ sharp	7.15 μ sharp	—	8.2-8.6 μ broad	—
Catechol H.A. (O ₂)	2.9-3.3 broad μ	3.45 μ sharp	5.85 μ weak	6.25 μ m. sharp	—	7.25 μ V. weak	8.2-8.6 μ broad	—
Hydrolysed catechol H.A. (Residue)	3.2 μ broad	—	5.85 μ hump	6.25 μ sharp	—	7.25 μ V. weak	8.45 μ shoulder	—
Hydrolysed hydroquinone H.A. (Residue)	2.9-3.3 μ broad	—	5.85 μ hump	6.25 μ sharp	—	—	8.0-8.5 μ broad	—
Hydroquinoneglycine polymer	3.0-3.3 μ broad	—	5.85 μ V. weak hump	6.25 μ sharp	6.65 μ V. sharp	7.45 μ V. weak	8.0-8.5 μ broad	—
Hydrolysed hydroquinone glycine polymer (Residue)	3.0-3.3 μ broad	—	5.85 μ V. weak hump	6.25 μ sharp	6.65 μ V. sharp	7.45 μ V. weak	8.0-8.5 μ broad	—
Glucose H.A. (40 hr)	2.9-3.2 μ broad	3.45 μ shoulder	5.85 μ V. sharp	6.25 μ sharp	6.65 μ sharp	7.25 μ weak	8.2-8.6 μ broad	9.8 μ sharp
Glucose H.A.	2.9-3.2 μ broad	3.45 μ hump	5.85 μ sharp	6.25 μ sharp	6.6 μ hump	7.25 μ broad	8.2-8.6 μ shoulder	9.8 μ sharp
Glucose hyatomelanic acid	2.9-3.2 broad	3.45 μ sharp	5.85 μ sharp	6.25 μ sharp	6.6 μ sharp	7.2 μ weak	8.3 μ broad	9.8 μ weak
Hydrolysed catechol H.A. (by O ₂) (Residue)	2.9-3.4 μ broad	—	5.85 μ weak	6.25 μ sharp	—	—	8.4 μ shoulder	—

TABLE 2 ANALYSIS OF I.R. SPECTRA OF SYNTHETIC HUMIC SUBSTANCES.

Wave length (μ)	Proposed assignment
2.9-3.0	H—bonded OH
3.3	Aromatic CH
3.4-3.5	Aliphatic CH ₂ and CH ₃
5.8-5.9	Vibration of carboxyl C=O (carbonyl) in aromatic and aliphatic acids.
6.25	Stretching vibrations of conjugated C=C carbon bonds, C=O in quinones, stretching vibrations of —C=N—in heterocyclic nitrogen compounds.
6.6-6.7	Aromatic C=C.
7.15	CH stretch of methyl
7.25-7.3	Aliphatic CH ₂ and CH ₃
8.-8.5	C—O—C stretch frequencies of aromatic ethers.
9.8	—C—, —C—OH—and—C—C—C— vibrations typical of sugar rings and glucosidic linkages.

From the spectra, the presence of the following groups has been suggested: Polymerically bonded-OH groups, free carboxyl and carboxylate groups, side chain CH₂ and CH₃ groups and c=c-vibrations of aromatic ring system. From the study made here it can be said that inspite of different starting materials as well as different techniques of preparations, the synthetic humic acids resemble closely each other in their i. r spectra and also they have striking similarities in this respect with their natural counterpart.

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Oxine Complexes of Quinquevalent Molybdenum-Di-8 hydroxyquinolinium Oxopentabromomolybdate(V) and its derivatives.

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IN continuation of our investigation on the co-ordination chemistry of molybdenum we report here the isolation and study of oxine complexes of quinquevalent molybdenum. It is already known¹⁻² that the chemistry of molybdenum in oxidation state five is mainly dominated by the oxometal ions MoO³, Mo₂O₃⁴⁺ and Mo₂O₄²⁺. We have isolated (Oxine H₂)₂ [MoOBr₅] and [Mo₂O₄ (Oxine)₂ (H₂O)₂] (where oxineH = 8-hydroxyquinoline) and characterised them by analytical and various other by physicochemical methods.

Experimental

All reagents used were of A. R. grade. *Analyses*: Molybdenum and bromine were estimated³ gravimetrically as MoO₃ and AgBr respectively. Nitrogen was estimated by Dumas' method.

Preparation Di-8-hydroxy quinolinium oxopentabromomolybdate (V), (OxineH₂)₂[MoOBr₅]: 1g of molybdenum trioxide was dissolved in 15 ml of concentrated hydrobromic acid (48%) with gentle heating and the solution was evaporated to brown moist solid. This was taken up in solution with 10 ml of hydrobromic acid and to this was added 5 ml hydrobromic acid solution of 1.5g of 8-hydroxyquino-